

THE PRODUCTION MODELS, PRODUCTS DIVERSIFICATION, SEARCH FOR NEW MARKETS, POSSIBLE RISKS AND SOLUTIONS.

F.S.Abdullayev¹

The PhD Mr.

B.J.Makhkamov²

R.A.Islamov³

F.Sh.Komilov⁴

R.F.Abdullayev⁵

The Central production warehouse of
“O‘zbek Geologiya Qidiruv” JSC

¹⁻²⁻³⁻⁴⁻⁵Tashkent State Technical University

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Annotation: In the case study, using the example of the Central Production Base of O‘zbek Geologiya Qidiruv JSC, considers the possibilities of diversifying production, achieving new economic indicators, as well as considering the use of different sales methods, entering new markets and strategic planning for the further growth of the enterprise.

Key words: production, import substitution, localization, labor resources, jobs, markets, sales, income, profit, diversification, strategy, planning, risks.

The enterprise was founded in the 1960s of the last century, specializes in the production of products aimed at providing drilling rigs with the necessary spare parts, mining and drilling tools, etc. The enterprise has been preserved and operates, being under the supervision of the country's geological industry, producing products to this day.

The activity of the enterprise is relevant to this day, the work of the enterprise pursues three strategically important goals, this is the creation of jobs for the local people, import substitution and localization.

Nowadays, the company employs about a hundred employees, specialists and workers.

The main targets of the enterprise, as already mentioned above, is the production of various kinds of mining and drilling tools, spare parts for drilling rigs, as well as the development of new products and the diversification of various types of other specialized products, at the moment, the production of approximately 178 types of different types of products for the industry has been mastered.

Figure No.1. The production chain of the manufacturing mining and drilling tools, as well as spare parts for drilling rigs.

In same time with the manufacturing of spare parts of drilling rigs, technical water carrier trucks and other special equipment based on the chassis of trucks is being actively developed, it is planned to develop this area is instead of various types of auxiliary equipment and / or technical, residential and other premises on the chassis of truck vehicles.

Figure No.2. The production chain of the manufacturing of special technics.

In order to maintain the production process, it is necessary to work out issues with the technical equipment of the enterprise, step by step to update and modernize the production fleet of machine tools and machines that are on the balance sheet of the enterprise, and introduce an automated production system. Let out production should correspond to the established norms and requirements of quality standards of the international level.

To qualitatively raise the level of providing conditions and remuneration for workers and specialists. To involve in the production process specialists who know their work well, who understand the labor-intensive production process well. Today, finding and finding good specialists with skills and work experience seems to be difficult, therefore, the drain of personnel and their retention in their jobs is a very difficult process for any enterprise that must find opportunities to stimulate its specialists at the proper level, through timely

payment of wages, bonuses, social packages, working and rest conditions and other opportunities.

The next thing that is also important in the life of an enterprise is the formation of prices for products. It is known that the price is formed from production costs and profits, but in order for the sale of finished products, it is necessary that prices correspond to the established price conjecture formed on the market by other suppliers of similar products, be it another local manufacturer or imported products supplied from foreign countries. Along with this, a clear understanding will come of how competitive products an enterprise can produce, which of them is profitable to produce, and which one should be abandoned, this strategy was studied in detail in the scientific work “Marketing Maneuvers. Modern Approaches to Profit, Growth and Renewal” by American economist and marketer Philip Kotler.

It is important to study and adopt the international experience of other developed countries such as China, South Korea or others. The experience of enterprises of the same level will help our company develop and apply in the future strategies for promoting finished products to other markets of near and far foreign countries.

At present, it is the analysis of development on the example of foreign countries that is subject to in-depth analysis and study of the strategy for promoting products for export and is subject to identifying strengths and weaknesses, as well as identifying all possible existing risks, which we will discuss in detail and set out in the future.

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